

THE ROLE OF THE STEAM APPROACH IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE EDUCATION SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

The article discusses and analyzes the role of the STEM approach in the development of the education system. The importance of STEM education in the preparation of competitive human capital for Industry 4.0 is substantiated. The STEM approach offers the systematic introduction of a new, engineering and technological aspect of education based on a digital platform into the school.

Keywords: modernization, technology, technological progress, innovation, robotization, education, high-tech industries, science, technology, engineering.

The modern rapidly changing world poses ever new tasks for humanity, the solutions of which require dynamism. As you know, scientific and technological progress is the progressive development of science and technology, the result of which is the consistent modernization of equipment, technologies and production organizations, increasing their efficiency.

The developed countries of the 21st century are characterized by a competitive economy with Industry 4.0, with competitive science and education that meet the needs of Society 4.0. In Industry 4.0, economic growth is based not on natural resources, but on innovation and competitive human capital.

The high-tech production of Industry 4.0 involves not only the use, but also the development of the process of digitalization and robotization of industry (the use of quantum computers, artificial intelligence, IoT technologies, big data, etc.), as well as the dynamic updating of technologies and equipment.

Thus, Industry 4.0, the “smart economy”, poses completely new challenges for the education system. The social request of the Society 4.0 is “correspondence of the educational paradigm to the industrial paradigm of Industry 4.0”. According to foreign experts, specialists must possess key educational competencies and are distinguished by high scientific, digital, and engineering and technological training [2].

The specialists of the future should be ready for mobile adaptation to new conditions, acquiring new skills in order to keep up with changes in the labor market and dynamically developing innovations in technology. Therefore, for the development of the education system in a rapidly changing environment, the conceptual model “lifelong learning” is of particular importance.

The largest USA companies have declared that school and university education does not meet the

needs of dynamically developing high-tech industries. After analyzing the situation, the USA National Science Foundation in 2001 proposed introducing the STEM approach to modernize the American education system [2]. The main components of STEM education - science, technology and engineering, as well as mathematics and ICT cover all areas of modern life, are the main indicators of the functioning and development of Industry 4.0. This provision actualizes the importance of the STEM approach in the preparation of competitive human capital for Industry 4.0. Therefore, STEM education is essentially a response to the challenges of the dynamic industrial-digital era of human development.

The new industrial paradigm requires higher education to rank at or above 'University 4.0' or at least 'University 3.0'. As you know, "University 1.0" is a university that conducts high-quality educational activities. "University 2.0" - educational and scientific activities. "University 3.0" carries out educational, scientific and entrepreneurial activities, i.e. fulfills the order of high-tech industries. "University 4.0", in addition to the listed functions of "University 3.0", is able to solve the problems of modern industry by changing the concept of the industry itself, to become a leader in the development of high-tech industries [2].

Currently, the USA, England, China, South Korea, Singapore, Turkey and other developed countries are systematically implementing STEM education based on the adopted state programs.

In the CIS countries, there is still no systematic approach to introducing the concept of STEM education into educational standards. In Russia, the introduction of this trend into federal state educational standards is being implemented in a peculiar way.

Since 2014, engineering education has been given priority in the Russian Federation. In 2019, a new concept of the subject area "Technology" was developed taking into account the requirements of the STEM approach.

In Kazakhstan, there is no unified approach to the implementation of the ideas of STEM education. Some advanced schools (NIS, BINOM, etc.) are implementing elements of the STEM approach, characterized mainly by the study of the initial foundations of "Robotics", laboratory work using ICT and the use of design and research methods in the educational process.

In the STEM approach, the personality-activity and functional-competence approaches to system modernization are interrelated. Instead of the "knowledge" paradigm of education, the activity approach proposed by J. Dewey in the last century "learning through activity" is applied here.

The activity approach means that at the center of the educational process is the personality (subject of activity), its goals, motives, needs, and the main tool for self-realization and self-development of the personality is activity.

The essence of the personal-activity approach in teaching is not to fill ready-made knowledge in the head of a person, but to direct all practical measures to the organization of intensive, gradually becoming more complex creative activity.

Interacting with the world through activity and in the process of productive cognitive activity, there is an independent acquisition of knowledge and self-actualization of the individual [3].

The study showed that the pedagogical technology of the three-dimensional methodological system of education, based on the platform of the didactic matrix, makes it possible to implement teaching not only on the basis of personal-activity and functional-competence approaches, but also on the STEM approach [3].

As is known, the competence-based approach is a system of requirements for education, which assumes the results of education in the form of competencies and contributes to the practice-oriented nature of the training of students, strengthening the role of their independent work in resolving problems and situations. In this approach, practical tasks prevail over theoretical knowledge and orient students to apply knowledge in different situations and new circumstances [3]. The competence-based approach includes the main concept of the activity approach - "learning through activity" and strengthens it with the requirement that the student must be able to apply the acquired knowledge in practice.

Thus, the competence-based approach is aimed at the formation of functional literacy, which characterizes a person's ability to use the knowledge acquired during life to solve a wide range of life tasks in various spheres of human activity. The international PISA quality study measures the functional literacy of 15-year-olds. The purpose of this study is to find out whether students at the age of 15 (in many foreign countries at this age children receive compulsory general education) have the knowledge and skills they need to fully function in modern society.

Depending on the hierarchy of the content of education, competencies are divided into subject, interdisciplinary and key. Subject competence is characterized by the ability to apply the acquired knowledge within the content of one subject in solving practical problems. Practical and laboratory-experimental work play an important role in the formation of subject competence.

Experience shows that achieving the goal at the level of "application", then "creation" involves strengthening the intra-subject entertaining and applied potential of the content of disciplines.

Consequently, the formation of the subject competence of students requires the modernization of the content of subjects in the context of increasing the share of practical, laboratory and experimental research classes in the curriculum.

The formation of interdisciplinary competencies involves the development of integrated content with an applied purpose from the subject area of school disciplines in the context of classes.

The integration of the content of the NMC subjects with an applied orientation opens the way for the creative, productive activity of the student to achieve the goal at the level of "application", hereinafter referred to as "creation".

Therefore, the modern theory of the content of education is faced with the task of finding the optimal combination of fundamental and applied aspects of educational material, taking into account the specifics of each subject, necessary for the formation of subject and interdisciplinary competencies. The solution of this problem requires a scientifically based revision of the principles for selecting the content of secondary education in the context of the requirements of the competency-based approach. The results of this area of research would serve as a scientific basis for determining a reasonable list of "cross-cutting" topics, constructing the content, the so-called "phenomenal education".

Therefore, a distinctive feature of the content of STEM education is practice-oriented, the introduction of the subject area "Technology" into the curriculum instead of the subject "Labor", and engineering methods in order to form engineering and technological thinking and skills.

As you know, technology is a set of methods and methods of work, their mode, sequence of actions, materials and tools to achieve the desired result.

In a broad sense, engineering is the use of scientific principles and innovation to design and build a wide range of facilities. Engineering involves the use of scientific innovations in solving real applied problems, which contributes to the development of the skills of an inventor and innovator among specialists.

Thus, the STEM approach offers, first of all, the systematic introduction of a new, engineering and technological aspect of education into the school based on a digital platform.

In traditional education, the subjects of the NMC: physics, mathematics, chemistry, biology, and computer science are studied separately, their content does not intersect with each other in any way, leaving scattered pieces of information in the student's memory.

The subject area "Technology" allows you to build logical connections between these disciplines, look at the world around you globally, and learn the patterns more deeply.

Thus, STEM education involves: 1) the transition from a purely fundamental approach to studying the subjects of the STEM to studying them in the context of the practical application of scientific knowledge in solving applied problems from real life; 2) strengthening the applied, practical and laboratory-experimental components of the content of the subjects of the NMC; 3) Determining the content of the subject "Technology" by integrating the content of the subjects of the NMC, informatics and robotics in order to gradually master

various technologies, form engineering and technological skills; 4) The use of robotics in the laboratory and experimental work of subjects of the NMC.

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